

CLUMPAK main pipeline - Job 1664938376 summary

Major modes for the uploaded data:

K=1

K=2

K=3

K=4

K=5

K=6

K=7

K=8

K=9

K=10

Minor modes for the uploaded data:

K=3 MinorCluster1

K=6 MinorCluster1

K=7 MinorCluster1

K=8 MinorCluster1

K=9 MinorCluster1

K=10 MinorCluster1

Division of runs by mode:

K=1 10/10
K=2 10/10
K=3 7/10, 3/10
K=4 10/10
K=5 10/10
K=6 9/10, 1/10
K=7 9/10, 1/10
K=8 9/10, 1/10
K=9 9/10, 1/10
K=10 9/10, 1/10